

The LEGOPardo Experience

Motivational control demonstrations for cadets

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Given the variety of topics that comprise a bachelor program, even the most motivated students may find themselves lacking interest in a particular subject. A relevant example are service academies, where students usually have a strong military vocation but their interest in other apparently unrelated but mandatory topics cannot be taken for granted. In these situations, teachers face the challenge of engaging the interest of students and promoting the usefulness of the subject for their careers. Videos with possible applications [1] or laboratory experiments with real systems [2] are some of the multiple resources a teacher can use to stimulate the students. However, making the theoretical lessons appealing is also important.

This article describes an experience on improving the motivation of Spanish cadets towards the subject of automatic control, as well as showing them the usefulness of control theory in their future profession. As prospective officers of the army, these students are required to obtain an engineering degree as part of their formation. This experience attempts to capture their interest by introducing a set of demonstrations in the theory sessions that highlight the relationship between control concepts and their professional environment. (“The role of control in

the Spanish military education” further describes the military career in Spain and its engineering contents.) These demonstrations are an efficient and affordable complement to laboratory sessions and, being the thread that runs through theory contents, aim to improve cadets’ attention from the very beginning and during the whole course with a model drawn from their expertise interest.

Specifically, a model of an armored car has been designed. The course has been oriented to model and analyze the turret’s aiming subsystem, and to explain its feedback control scheme. The tank (see Fig. 1) has been built with a LEGO NXT Mindstorms Robotics Invention System and has been named *LEGOPardo* as a wink to the tanks in service in the Spanish army, the *Leopardo 2E*.

The NXT LEGO MindStorms [3] have been used for educational purposes in a wide variety of courses such as signal processing [4], discrete-event systems [5] and robotics [6], [7]. These LEGO devices are also not new to the subject of automatic control [8]. In [9], LEGO pieces are used to design a motor with several gears, and laboratory sessions are presented in [10].

From the technical point of view we contribute an introductory-suited linear time-invariant (LTI) system model based on NXT with a complete overview in the Laplace domain, seen both as a 2nd- and 3rd-order model and highlighting the teaching possibilities the latter opens over the former. This comprehensive description may serve as inspiration for other similarly built systems.

The LEGOPardo

Our aim is to present the main theoretical concepts of the course in such a way that cadets establish a correspondence between theory and its practical effects using a model system that is related to their professional activity.

Given their background, the choice of the real system is the gun turret of an armored vehicle. On the one hand, it can be naively modeled as a dc motor based electromechanical system that exemplifies the course topics; on the other hand, it is a system strongly familiar to the students. Thus, the course demonstrations are based on modeling, analyzing and controlling the turret aiming system.

The LEGO NXT Mindstorms [3] have been chosen as the hardware to build the model of the system because of their affordability. The tank has been assembled devoting one motor to the turret angular position (see Fig. 2), with a laser pointer mounted on the gun to easily observe where it is pointing. Besides, thanks to their versatility, LEGO models can be conveniently adapted to other contexts while retaining the learning outcomes.

Given that the subject tackles SISO linear systems, and that most of the course is explained in the Laplace domain, the LEGOPardo is modeled using a block diagram with different linear transfer functions. This block diagram is represented in Fig. 3. The model contains all the elements that appear in the course: a feedback loop, a proportional controller and a transfer function of the real system. In the figure, $\theta_r(s)$ represents the reference signal (the desired orientation of the turret), and $\theta_y(s)$ the actual orientation of the turret, as reported by the motor encoder. The error is denoted by $E(s)$ and $U(s)$ is the velocity input sent to the LEGOPardo. The

current design considers only a proportional controller in the demonstrations, which seems to be sufficient to illustrate most of the concepts of the course. The use of more advanced controllers such as a PID is left for future work.

Since the internals of a LEGO motor are unknown without breaking it open, an attempt is not made to axiomatically model the turret during the first lessons. Instead, by means of response-fitting optimization techniques we have approximated a 2nd-order transfer function of the turret in the work regime of the demonstrations and then obtained a plausible model from the latter. The system is described in the Laplace domain as

$$G(s) = \frac{\theta_y(s)}{U(s)} = \frac{161}{s(s + 16)}. \quad (1)$$

The model has one pole at the origin, given that the input to the LEGOPardo is a velocity command and the output is the angular position of the motor, and it is used for demonstrations up to and including the root locus one. At that point we present and elaborate on a higher-order, more precise model, when it becomes convenient for the progress of the course.

If we consider a standard dc motor with negligible inductance, its transfer function can be expressed as

$$\frac{\Theta(s)}{V_r(s)} = \frac{K_i}{s(RJs + RB + K_e K_i)}. \quad (2)$$

Our 2nd-order model corresponds, for example, to a moment of inertia $J = 1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^2$, viscous friction $B = 1.44 \times 10^{-2} \text{ N m s/rad}$, and circuit resistance $R = 6.21 \times 10^{-2} \Omega$. Back emf and torque constants are taken as $K_e = K_i = 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ N m/A}$ and V s/rad , respectively. These example values may help students bridge the gap between the physical system and its transfer function.

Demonstrations

This section details all the demonstrations carried out during the lectures in order to illustrate the theoretical concepts with the LEGOPardo.

Introduction to the course

The first demonstration is performed during the first lecture, in order to motivate the cadets as soon as possible about the possibilities of automatic control in their professional careers. The objective of the demonstration is to introduce the LEGOPardo and to show how it can be controlled.

Two volunteers are asked to manually control two “different” turret models using a joystick, with the objective of aiming at a hypothetical target drawn on the blackboard. The first volunteer controls a turret with high gain, resulting in fast motions for small commands of the joystick. Consequently, the cadet finds it hard to properly aim the gun, in most cases pointing to somewhere else, sometimes towards their classmates, to their amusement. The second volunteer faces the problem of aiming a turret with a small gain, which moves with high precision but slowly when compared to the first one. In this case, the cadet is able to correctly aim to the target but requiring a significant amount of time.

Afterwards, the turret is aimed to the reference target position using two different proportional controllers ($K = 1$ and $K = 5$) and feedback. The angular position of the turret in the four scenarios is depicted in Fig. 4. When this graph is shown to the cadets, they can realize the advantages of automatic control. Therefore, this demonstration promotes a positive attitude

towards the course from the beginning.

Step response of second-order systems

This demonstration illustrates the different responses exhibited by a 2nd-order system when excited by a step input depending on the damping ratio. It serves to reinforce concepts like overshoot and peak time, as well as the different standard parameters used to describe a 2nd-order system.

In order to obtain different responses from the system, the LEGOPardo runs in the previously described closed-loop setup (Fig. 3). The closed-loop transfer function obtained once a proportional controller K is introduced has the form

$$W(s) = \frac{161K}{s(s + 16) + 161K} = \frac{161K}{s^2 + 16s + 161K}. \quad (3)$$

By adjusting the proportional gain, different responses from the system are achieved when seen as an open-loop 2nd-order one (Fig. 5). However, since at this point of the course the cadets are not familiar with what a proportional controller is, details of the closed-loop implementation are skipped. These details are shown, more fittingly, in the root locus demonstration. Instead, a motivating explanation is given as if different turrets were being considered, for example of different masses, as in the introductory demonstration. This way, the importance of the actual physical system and the modeling phase is also highlighted.

After the demonstration, the students have witnessed the different 2nd-order responses and their relevant characteristics, relating them to the underlying theoretical concepts.

Empirical second-order response identification

This demonstration is designed to exemplify in a backwards fashion the concepts presented in the previous one. A typical underdamped response is produced in the LEGOPardo, and the cadets are asked to find the system transfer function by measuring the theoretical characteristics just learned in the time response.

The most prominent characteristics that usually catch the cadets' attention are the peak time and the output value at that time, which compared to the steady-state value provides the overshoot. With this information, the cadets compute a 2nd-order model for the transfer function of the LEGOPardo. Figure 6 compares the output from the model computed by the cadets, the feedback model with transfer function (1) and $K = 1.25$, and the real output. In the figure it is also highlighted the peak value, which gives an overshoot $OS = 0.1125$ and a peak time $T_P = 0.28$ s.

The imperfect overlap in the plot provides the opportunity to briefly point out real issues such as non-linearities in the motor, boundedness of the control actions/signals and similar issues that appear when analyzing and controlling a real system, even if they are beyond the scope of the subject.

One particularly interesting result of this demonstration is that the cadets themselves obtain the transfer function of the LEGOPardo turret, which they could not model directly since the innards of the LEGO motor and precise masses of physical components are not available to them.

After the demonstration, students have witnessed the influence of 2nd-order parameters,

which are key concepts through the rest of the course. These parameters are later identified from specifications during control sessions, which usually present more difficulties to students, and by remembering this and later demonstrations their implications on real systems can be quickly pointed out.

Effect of perturbations

This experiment demonstrates the advantages of using feedback compensation compared to open-loop controllers. Many cadets have problems visualizing the advantages of using feedback. From their point of view, open-loop systems are easier to work with than closed-loop systems because the underlying math is simpler.

First of all, the advantages are presented from an analytical point of view and then a practical experiment is set up. The first step consists on showing the behavior of three different compensators used to reach the same goal, which is to aim at a target 50 degrees away from the initial position, without any external perturbation. One of the controllers is designed in open-loop while the other two represent different instances of the closed-loop system shown in Fig. 3. Figure 8a shows the results of this part of the experiment presented to the cadets. It is pointed out that, independently of the response type, the system is capable of reaching the reference value regardless of the used controller. Next, a perturbation is produced, caused by an elastic band that anchors the turret to a rod integral with the LEGOPardo structure and that impedes its free movement (Fig. 7). When the turret is displaced from its zero degrees position (where the elastic band is at rest) a force is generated by the band. This force, which opposes the displacement, is proportional to the lengthening of the band itself and therefore grows with the

angular displacement of turret until becoming constant when the transient state ends.

The responses of the system under the same inputs are presented in Fig. 8b. This time none of the compensators reach the reference with zero steady-state error. However, it is highlighted that the closed-loop compensators display a better behavior than the open-loop one: larger gains gradually reduce the steady-state error caused by the perturbation, although at the cost of more overshoot.

Analysis and control using the root locus

This demonstration illustrates the use of root locus techniques to analyze and control the LEGOPardo, while reinforcing root locus concepts.

The demonstration is highly related to the step-response one, as indeed both use the same setup. However, at this point of the course cadets have a broader knowledge of the subject and are able to understand all the concepts related with controlling a system that were bypassed previously. In particular, the unitary feedback loop which is at the core of the root locus diagram can be discussed in detail.

The demonstration starts by presenting the complete block diagram of the LEGOPardo turret subsystem, shown in Fig. 3, with the 2nd-order transfer function used earlier as the model, Eq. (1). The root locus plot is done using the commonly used rules, obtaining a sketch with two vertical asymptotes.

Analyzing the root locus, a discussion is promoted about the implications of using different gains in the proportional controller for the closed-loop response, and on how the root

locus can help in quickly predicting the behavior of the system with a particular controller.

At this time some cadets may observe that by obtaining the 2nd-order parameters from the closed-form equation they are equally able to predict the system behavior. In any case, the 2nd-order dominant poles of the system for several K values are identified using the same peak-overshoot measurements done in the empirical identification demonstration. Surprisingly for the students, the obtained poles do not line-up with the presented root locus sketch. Instead, the poles progressively close on the imaginary axis (Fig. 9).

Indeed, it turns out that the turret can be better modeled by a higher-order system. If we consider a non-negligible inductance, Eq. (2) becomes

$$\frac{\Theta(s)}{V_r(s)} = \frac{K_i}{s(LJs^2 + (RJ + LB)s + RB + K_e K_i)}. \quad (4)$$

Knowing this, a 3rd-order model is presented,

$$G(s) = \frac{9922}{s(s + 21)(s + 54)}, \quad (5)$$

found with the same techniques as Eq. (1). In the physical model this could correspond, approximately, to $L = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ H, $B = 1.82 \times 10^{-2}$ N m s/rad, $R = 5.74 \times 10^{-2}$ Ω , with the remaining values as in the 2nd-order example. Conveniently, this finding serves to reinforce the idea of dominating poles; that is, that the response of a particular instance can be approximated (with the necessary precautions) as a 2nd-order system even though we now know that, globally, the system must be of higher order. After sketching the new root locus, the cadets observe that it agrees with the measurements, and that it conveys more information than using only the parameters identified from an equation.

Furthermore, a new observation can be made: the system theoretically becomes unstable

for large-enough values of K . Empirically it is demonstrated that the LEGOPardo can indeed become so, although after a certain time the oscillation amplitude does not grow anymore (Fig. 10). Again, a discussion on boundedness of motor action ensues; motors are unable to provide all the actuation the controller asks of them. In the particular case of LEGO motors the programming interface rejects values over the maximum, so instead this saturation must be considered in the control software. “Control software of the LEGOPardo” provides more details about the used control software.

Once the demonstration is finished, the concept of root locus and the effects of varying the gain of a proportional controller are clearer to the cadets. The demonstration helps them to understand that the root locus sketch conveys at a glance the whole spectrum of behaviors for a particular system with a proportional controller. Finally, the dominant poles in the 3rd-order model stress the point that these control techniques usually try to approximate a 2nd-order behavior by ensuring dominance of the desired poles according to specifications.

Frequency response using Bode plots

The last demonstration displays the frequency response of the LEGOPardo for periodical inputs, relating this information to the Bode plot of the transfer function. The goal is to demonstrate the meaning of the Bode plot and the way it can be obtained through the analysis of the real system. The LEGOPardo is fed with periodic command inputs of constant amplitude and different frequencies while the output angular position of the turret is logged. Then, each output is compared to the corresponding input in terms of amplitude and phase shift.

The results of this experiment for a set of 12 different frequencies are shown in Fig. 11.

The red line represents the reference input while the blue one shows the output position of the turret. The cadets observe that, for low frequency inputs, the reference and output signal do match almost exactly, implicating that both amplitude and phase shifts (represented by the gap between the red and blue horizontal and vertical lines respectively) are negligible. As the frequency increases, so does the phase shift, while the amplitude decreases. This phenomenon matches students' intuition, in the sense that is more difficult to accurately track a rapidly moving target than a slow one.

After the analysis of amplitude and phase shift, it is demonstrated to the cadets how these variations can be used to generate the Bode plot associated to the transfer function of the system. Each amplitude input-output ratio represents a point of the Bode's amplitude graph at a certain frequency, and phase-shift values conversely represent a point of the Bode's phase graph. These points are shown in Fig. 12, along with the plots obtained from the closed-loop transfer functions (with $K = 1.25$) derived from the open-loop Eqs. (1) and (5). These plots transmit the relationship between the Bode graph, transfer function and analysis of a real system to cadets.

After the demonstration, cadets are more familiar with the frequency response of a real system, having observed that both input and output signals have the same frequency but different amplitudes and phases, which are described by the Bode plot they learn to sketch.

Findings

The classes are imparted within the military academy at Zaragoza, which applies some particular rules to its students. These rules in some cases limit venues of evaluation: attendance to sessions is mandatory, which coupled with the subject being not optional, precludes any

“popularity” measurements based on enrollment or dropout.

However, Universidad de Zaragoza has quality controls in the form of anonymous polls, performed each semester, in which students give their opinion on subjects and professors assigned to them. These polls contain two questions that are particularly pertinent for the purpose of analyzing if the LEGOPardo demonstrations fulfill their purpose, which are summarized in Fig. 13. Data for the years before and after the LEGOPardo was brought into the classroom are included. Numerical values can be found in Table I. Polls are rated from one to five (here shown as stars for clarity), in a typical *Totally disagree* to *Totally agree* spectrum.

There is a clear improvement of the students’ perception about the course for both questions. Note that in 2011 there were six groups, whereas there were nine in 2012, making the size of groups slightly larger in that case. The most interesting result is the change in perception to the second question, which directly addresses the purposes of the LEGOPardo: helping military cadets realize that automatic systems are not only ubiquitous in their future work, but that knowing more about them from an engineering point of view makes them better officers. For that question, the percent of students that saw no interest at all in the course halved, while the percent of them that were at least indifferent went from the minority to the majority.

It is also remarkable that, for the first question about learning satisfaction, the percent of unsatisfied students (one and two ratings) went from over 50% to below 20%. Since no other methodological changes exist between these years but the LEGOPardo, it is not unreasonable to consider that the LEGOPardo has improved the cadets’ perception of the subject.

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Figure 1. The LEGOPardo. The picture was taken in the grounds of the *Academia General Militar* of Zaragoza, with a larger “cousin” in the background.

Figure 2. Relevant components of the LEGOPardo tank. The turret subsystem, with its mounted laser pointer, is used in the demonstrations.

Figure 3. Block diagram used to control the LEGOPardo. A standard feedback loop is used, being the input and output, respectively, the desired and actual orientation of the turret.

Figure 4. The motivation experiment. Cadets struggle with unfriendly control configurations. Then, two automatic controllers are demonstrated that easily outperform their efforts.

(a) Overdamped, $K = 0.2$.

(b) Critically damped, $K = 0.4$.

(c) Slightly underdamped, $K = 1$.

(d) Underdamped, $K = 4$.

Figure 5. Predicted and observed 2nd-order responses for several gains. The experiment is repeated using several values of K to show the different kind of responses.

Figure 6. Estimation experiment. Peak time and overshoot are measured in the 2nd-order response, leading to an estimated 2nd-order model. The model obtained in this particular instance (“estimation”) is slightly different to the one used across this article (“model”).

Figure 7. Detail of the perturbation experiment. An elastic band is used to apply a perturbation to the turret.

(a) Unperturbed system.

(b) Perturbed system.

Figure 8. Effect of a perturbation on open-loop and closed-loop systems. When no perturbation exists, all controllers achieve the reference value. After applying a disturbance, the open-loop controller is the worst one among the studied controllers.

Figure 9. Root locus of the 3rd order model. Shown dominant poles are estimated from the response for values of gain $K = 1, 1.25, 1.67, 2.5$.

Figure 10. Unstable response for high values of gain ($K = 11$). The model response grows with unbounded amplitude. The LEGOPardo motors do not accept unbounded inputs, so they were saturated at the software level, limiting the amplitude of the actual response.

Figure 11. Periodic runs for Bode sampling. Each instance plots reference (red continuous lines) and output orientation (blue continuous lines) versus time for a specific frequency. Phase and gain points taken for measurement are marked by parallel straight lines (red and blue dotted lines).

Figure 12. Experimentally obtained Bode plot compared to LEGOPardo models. Sampling frequencies are identified by dots and were chosen to be logarithmically spaced.

(a)

(b)

Figure 13. Relevant questions in the anonymous student polls. There is improvement in the students' perception of the subject for both questions after the introduction of the LEGOPardo in the year 2012.

Year	*	**	***	****	*****	Students
<i>“I feel satisfied with what I have learned”</i>						
2011	29	19	21	12	6	87
2012	16	11	46	46	26	145
<i>“I find the course useful for my formation”</i>						
2011	39	14	16	12	6	87
2012	29	24	42	33	18	146

TABLE I
 POLL QUESTIONS RELEVANT TO THE LEGOPARDO DEPLOYMENT.

Sidebar 1: The role of control in the Spanish military education

Providing a broad education to future military officers is one of the primary concerns of the defense departments of developed countries [11], [12], [13]. Engineering knowledge is essential in their professional lives, as nowadays it is hard to imagine any complex military system that does not include advanced technologies. The Spanish government is not an exception in this regard, and cadets of its three military academies have traditionally received a strong formation in the sciences.

In 2007 the Spanish government went a step further by mandating that the technical formation of future officials be provided under the umbrella of public universities [14]. New officers under this plan of studies are awarded a joint degree for their military career (they become lieutenants) and an official B.Sc. degree by a public Spanish university.

In the case of the Spanish army (ground forces), whose cadets are formed at the *Academia General Militar* at Zaragoza, it is the *Centro Universitario de la Defensa* [15], affiliated with *Universidad de Zaragoza*, the one in charge of providing the formation conducive to the degree of *Ingeniería en Organización Industrial*. This degree can be roughly described as a mixed formation rooted in both mechanical engineering and business management. The degree was selected for army officers due to its adequacy for future professionals that have to be skilled both in the sciences and in people and resource management. The complete subject plan is available online [16].

Part of this degree is the *Sistemas Automáticos* [17] subject, a mandatory course of 60 tutored hours and 90 personal work hours, taught in the first semester of the third academic year.

Tutored hours are divided into theory classes and four laboratory sessions of two hours each, during which cadets work in couples on different problems related with the theoretical concepts using Matlab and Simulink.

This course is the only one devoted to modeling and control (albeit some later subjects apply or expand upon these topics, such is *Misiles* in the fourth year). Hence, the course is shaped as an introduction to classical control theory, with all the principles in mathematics and modeling that are necessary but not seen in previous courses. The course presents the main concepts contained in [18], [19], [20], [21], which are the reference books recommended to students.

The broad range of military systems and applications that make use of these concepts creates the perfect attraction to capture the interest of the cadets. Introducing a plausible physical model—namely, the LEGOPardo—enables to show in a real, military-inspired system the responses of periodic and aperiodic inputs or the benefits of using feedback compensation, to name a few.

Sidebar 2: Control software of the LEGOPardo

Matlab's Control System Toolbox is the software of choice for laboratory sessions. Students receive instruction on the course topics and are also encouraged to verify their homework with its free counterpart, Octave. Matlab is also a practical tool for immediate graphical feedback. In order to leverage this knowledge and given the existence of an NXT control library, Matlab is used too as the software underpinning the LEGOPardo demonstrations.

The RWTH toolbox [22] is a free open source toolbox, designed mainly for education purposes, developed at RWTH Aachen University to control Mindstorms with Matlab through Bluetooth or USB connections. The library application programming interface includes functions to handle all the capabilities of the NXT, as well as to read the different sensors available in the commercial box. Specifically for the purposes of the article, the library allows to send direct velocity commands to the motors and read their orientation through its integrated odometer. Therefore, the joint use of the cited library with Matlab makes it easy to compute the control signals, send them to the motors, read their output and plot the response establishing, ultimately, a simple control loop.

Although the NXT brick is a digital system, we point out to students that, with fast enough sampling rates (in our case of 10 ms), it is reasonable to study it as a continuous system. Students can observe this validity first-hand during laboratory sessions, where the discrete-step nature of Simulink simulations becomes apparent.

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